

Mating and Breeding Strategy of *Gambusia Affinis* (Baird and Giard, 1853): A Study

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Abstract

The present investigation aimed to study the mating and breeding tactics of *Gambusia affinis* (Baird and Giard, 1853). Rapid sexual maturity breeding habit, sex recognition, courtship and pair formation were some of the most important aspects of findings. Genopodium as a secondary accessory dimorphic feature in male along with gravid spot, ovoviviparity and superfaetation (producing number of broods from one mating) in female fish were promiscuous feature of reproductive biology of *Gambusia affinis*.

Keywords

Gambusia Affinis, Mating- Breeding Tactics, Commercial Value, Commercial Breeders.

Introduction

The fish of the poeceliidae family are the best known of all aquarium fish due to their relative ease of keep and the many colorful cultivated varieties available. *G. affinis* is one of the most renowned. Cosmopolitan fish in terms of its larvicidal nature is famous throughout the world. It is of great biological, ornamental, educational, commercial value and thereby having its peculiar importance.

Perhaps this has certainly triggered off many hobbyist, commercial breeders, exporters to systematically search for attractive species and varieties through artificial breeding techniques. A good knowledge on the biology, feeding behavior and ambient environmental condition of the fish species is a prerequisite for culture techniques. Keeping this in view the present study on *G. affinis* has been under taken to work out detailed reproductive behavior. Some important contributions on the said field of studies are from Evansw and Magurran (1999) and that of Pilastro and Bsazza (1999).

Objective of study

The present study on *G. affinis* has been under taken to work out detailed reproductive behavior.

Review of Literature

Some important contributions on the said field of studies are from Evansw and Magurran (1999), and that of Pilastro and Bsazza (1999), Emlen, S. T. and Orign, L. W. (1997), Singh, N. and Gupta, P.K.(2014).

Methodology

A set of 30 healthy adult male and female of *G. affinis* species of the same age group in the ratio 2:1 respectively were put in a glass aquarium of 24x12x12 inches filled with potable water. Netting, hanging, transporting and introducing fishes into an aquarium was done very carefully. Fishes that were healthy, having effortless swimming action and more active with clearly defined color patterns on them, were chosen, eliminating diseased fishes and those with visible anatomical deformities in order to obtain the most vigorous fry. The aquarium used was equipped with adequate illumination, meeting the requirements of the plants, filter, a thermostat, an aerator pump and the accessories. Another small sized aquarium of 12x6x6 inches was also prepared in the same manner possessing all the essential accessories as a breeding tank, to separate the female in to it after the mating, important factors influencing spawning and successful rearing of fry.

Result and Discussion

The males *G. affinis* were noted comparatively smaller, brighter, colorful and as a polygamous active members for mating preferences. The male were continuously in courtship display, always chasing after the females. The male were observed persistent drivers, so mating occurs frequently. Males sooner or later were send darting around a female, his fins spread and quivering. Acceptance of a male's advances is often signaled by head- shaking on the part of the female, followed by a dipping of the anterior part of her body (with a corresponding raising of the posterior half),which thus renders her genital aperture more accessible to the male once he adopts the correct mating position.

In order to fertilize the female, the anal fin of the male *G.affinis* developed into a structure known as "gonopodium", which inserts the packets of sperms into the female fish. It acts as the most significant external discriminatory feature between male and female and thereby, facilitating internal fertilization. The males were noted to count the female by approaching her and bending his body into 'S' shape. This type of behavior was repeated. As the male wings the gonopodium forward to make contact, the female will often fold her anal fin out of the way helping him even further. When mating, advancing from behind, male brought his gonopodium to a forward or sideways position due to its flexibility and insert it into the vent of the female.

After successful mating the females transferred to the breeding tank showed their chase fills out almost up to the head and her middle gets quite distended, as the days of delivery approaches. Females about to give were recognized by their round tight stomach, which in late pregnancy become cuboidal in shape. In the mature gravid female, slightly forward to the normal shaped anal fin inside her body appears a dark area known as the gravid spot. It was in fact considered to be the womb. As the eggs incubate, the eyes of fry are sometimes visible through the thin walls of the gravid spot (Figs.1-3).

About 4-8 week after mating, the females give birth up to 10-30 young's. At birth, the anal fin of the male *Gambusia* appears much like that of the female as he grows, the fin becomes gradually modified so that in a resting stage, it appears narrow and somewhat longer than that of the female.

Figure -1. (A&B) Gonopodium of male *Gambusia affinis*

Figure-2. Gravid Female fish of *Gambusia affinis* and male with modified Gonopodium

Figure-3. Live babies of *Gambusia affinis* (Mosquito fish)

At the age of 30-35 days the Sexes can be distinguished by the development of larger body of the female and her gravid spot which males do not show. The fry were noticed gaining fast maturity and within 3-4 months they get ready for taking part in a successful mating. The highest stage of evolution of parental care and breeding system is shown by viviparous teleosts (Baylis, 1981).

An interesting feature noticed in females that a fertile female have as many as half a dozen broods even if no males were present in the breeding tank. This behavior may be attributed as a precautionary measure and to store the packets of sperms ejected by the male and uses them to fertilize a series of eggs and hatchers as they ripen, following a single mating, females produces a number of fry at regular interval. This phenomenon is called superfaetation.

Table-1. Reproductive biology of *Gambusia affinis*

Sexual characteristics	Gestation period	Size	Temp.	pH	Hardness	No. of youngs delivered
Males i. Smaller in size ii. Brighter colourful iii. Active sexual partner iv. Gonopodium v. Attaining fast sexual maturity	4-6	3-4 cm	20-28° C	Slightly acidic 6-7	179 ppm	10-30
Females i. Comparatively large ii. Dull coloured iii. Pot-bellied iv. Prolific breeders v. Attaining fast sexual maturity vi. Ovoviviparity & superfaetation		5-7 cm				

Conclusion

The wide range of tolerance to physic-chemical parameters of water (Table- 1) and its adaptability and resilience along with superfaetation has made them suitable for aquarium life.

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